

Pest control and management OTHER PESTS

Rat activity in the deepwater rice area of Bangladesh

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Rats are serious pests of deepwater rice (DWR) in Bangladesh. In Apr to Dec 1982, we surveyed DWR areas of Tangail, Narsingdi, Manikganj, and Daudkandi to learn more about rat activity. In addition to DWR, boro rice and rabi crops — wheat,

watermelon, and bitter gourd — are grown in these areas.

Rat activity was measured by counting active rat burrow openings and recording the presence or absence of rat damage in pre-flood, flood, and postflood periods in fields and along shoulders of the highways that bisect the areas. Snap traps were used to catch rats for species identification. Three 1,500-m² plots were surveyed at each site during each crop season. Plots were 15-100 m from the highway.

Bandicota bengalensis was the only rat species trapped. During pre-flood (Apr

to mid-Jun) rats were found on highway shoulders and in all fields, but activity was concentrated in fields with boro rice and rabi crops (see table). Rats used highway shoulders as their main shelter during flood time (mid-Jun to Sep) and attacked floating DWR plants from there. When floodwater receded, they moved back to the dry DWR fields and made burrows, where they stored ripe rice panicles. The study suggests that rat damage could be effectively reduced by using poison baits and rat traps on highway shoulders during the flood. □

Rat activity in deepwater rice areas in Bangladesh during pre-flood, flood and postflood periods, BRRI, 1982.^a

Site	Preflood					Flood ^b		Postflood		
	Burrow openings/ha			Rat damage		Burrow openings/ha Highway shoulders	Rat damage in DWR fields	Burrow openings/ha		Rat damage in DWR fields
	Highway shoulders	DWR fields	Boro and rabi crop fields	DWR fields	Boro and rabi crop fields			Highway	DWR	
Tangail	2	2	42	-	+	106	+	4	162	+
Narsingdi	0	0	57	-	+	131	+	0	182	+
Manikganj	0	6	53	-	+	151	+	2	215	+
Daudkandi	4	0	46	-	+	86	+	0	141	+
Mean	1.5	2.0	49.5			118.5		1.5	177.5	

^aRat activity was measured by counting active rat burrow openings and by checking the presence (+) or absence (-) of rat damage. ^bDeepwater rice fields had 1-2.4 m water during flood time.

Irrigation and water management

Water use and costs of irrigating rice in Southwest Louisiana

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Southwest Louisiana is a major rice producing area in the United States. Topography is flat with poor surface and internal drainage. Generally, one rice crop is grown annually. Soils range from fine-textured, poorly drained clays in marshlands to coarser-textured, moderately well-drained silt loams along the northern and eastern fringes of the rice area.

An impervious subsoil 30 to 45 cm below the soil surface and a slow rate of surface water runoff cause poor soil aeration and a low soil moisture supply capacity. Rice irrigation wells are 75 to 100 m deep.

We conducted a survey to obtain data on water use and costs for rice irrigation from wells in southwest Louisiana. Specifications and annual volume of water pumped are in Table 1. The annual volume of water pumped — 736.7, 919.2, and

Table 1. Specifications and water use of representative rice irrigation wells in southwest Louisiana, 1982.

Well type	Diameter (cm)	Av well depth (m)	Flow rate (liters/s)	Average area irrigated (ha)	Annual volume of water pumped (million liters)
I	20.3	91.4	126.2	80.9	736.7
II	25.4	91.4	157.7	101.2	919.2
III	30.5	91.4	220.8	141.6	1,287.7